

Symphony: The Ultimate Wave Energy Controller?

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Abstract—In this paper, *Symphony*, a simple phase wave energy controller, is presented. The proposed controller bridges the gap between optimisation-based (OB) and non-optimisation-based (non-OB) strategies, preserving the implementation simplicity of non-OB control algorithms, but retaining the features and performance of OB strategies. Specifically, *Symphony* is the first non-OB controller capable of dynamically handling hard position, velocity, and force/torque constraints, while exhibiting close-to-optimal performance. Furthermore, *Symphony* is largely independent of the WEC model, which represents a seminal advancement; this feature is of pivotal importance, particularly considering the difficulties in accurate hydrodynamic modelling for WECs. Additionally, key features of *Symphony* include simplicity of design, implementation, tuning, and use, combined with robustness and versatility.

To illustrate the potential of *Symphony*, a comparison with spectral and model predictive WEC controllers is performed. The evaluated metrics are power absorption in constrained scenarios and computational efficiency. The results show above 90% of power absorption in constrained scenarios with respect to the constrained OB solutions, but with a significantly reduced computational burden, demonstrating that *Symphony* represents the ultimate wave energy controller, in terms of performance/complexity.

Index Terms—Wave energy, causal control, optimisation, energy maximisation, simplicity.

I. INTRODUCTION

CONTROL strategies are essential to maximise energy capture while managing operational constraints to protect wave energy converters (WECs) from damage [1]. Optimisation-based (OB) controllers, such as model predictive control [2], spectral methods [3], and moment-based algorithms [1] [4] provide, by

resorting to numerical routines, constrained energy-maximising solutions. However, the performance of OB strategies is highly dependent on the WEC model. Variations and uncertainties in the WEC dynamics, which appear during real-time operation, can severely compromise the use of OB strategies [5]. Additionally, in order to appropriately handle constraints, OB controllers require prediction of future wave elevation or excitation force, resulting in computationally expensive routines that ultimately hamper real-time implementation of these techniques. Importantly, although reducing the computational complexity of OB algorithms is possible, this may result in solutions that do not satisfy hard constraint requirements [6].

Alternatively, non-optimisation-based (non-OB) control strategies do not rely on numerical optimisation routines, and provide real-time (suboptimal) implementable solutions. However, none of the existing non-OB controllers are capable of effectively handling hard constraints, typically relying on controller detuning to retain safe operation [7] [8]. In addition, most of the existing non-OB controllers are dependent on a full WEC model, such as the LiTe-Con [9], the LiTe-Con+ [10], or the feedback resonating controller [11]. Other non-OB controllers, designed using an approximate velocity tracking structure (such as The Simple & Effective controller [12]), are dependent only on the WEC radiation dynamics [13]. Overall, in spite of the computational advantages, in terms of energy absorption, non-OB controllers have not yet reached the effectiveness of OB strategies.

To close the gap in performance between non-OB and OB control, this paper presents a novel non-OB controller, *Symphony*. *Symphony* obtains the highest levels of mechanical power absorption among non-OB controllers, while being (i) conceptually simple and largely insensitive to modelling errors, and (ii) the first causal controller capable of effectively and robustly handling hard position, velocity, and force constraints.

Symphony operates using a hierarchical structure. A higher decision level generates a suboptimal velocity reference proportional to the excitation force, effectively ‘phase matching’ the WEC velocity with the wave excitation force. On the other hand, a lower decision level includes a robust velocity tracking controller and a double reference conditioning system, designed to handle constraints. The first reference conditioning loop is tuned to robustly satisfy position and velocity constraints, by modulating the velocity reference with a Gaussian-like envelope function. Furthermore, by employing sliding-mode (SM) reference conditioning (SMRC), the second loop penalises the velocity profile

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to robustly keep the control force within the force constraints. Importantly, although the concept of phase synchronisation has already been studied, Symphony is the first non-OB controller to effectively amalgamate the requirements for position and force constraints, while retaining high levels of power absorption. Additionally, the possibility of designing Symphony as a controller largely independent of the WEC model is another fundamental feature of this proposal.

To evaluate the controller performance, this study compares Symphony with two state-of-the-art OB alternatives: A spectral controller (SP) [3] and model-predictive control (MPC) [2]. The results show that Symphony, without requiring optimisation or complex tuning, provides close-to-optimal (above 90%) levels of energy extraction across the evaluated sea states. The obtained results, combined with the significantly reduced computational burden, demonstrate the potential of Symphony as a wave energy controller.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. In Section II, the modelling framework, necessary to describe and analyse the dynamic behaviour of WECs, is introduced. In Section III, the Symphony controller is presented. The results obtained using Symphony, are presented in Section IV, and the main conclusions and findings are summarised in Section V.

II. CONTROL PRINCIPLES FOR WAVE ENERGY CONVERTERS

In this Section, the WEC modelling fundamentals are presented in Subsection II-A. Then, in Subsection II-B, the impedance matching principle for WECs is briefly discussed.

A. WEC modelling fundamentals

Applying Newton's second law, together with linear hydrodynamic assumptions [14], and a finite-order approximation for the radiation dynamics [15], the dynamics of a one-degree-of-freedom WEC can be described using:

$$\Sigma_w : \begin{cases} \dot{v} = \frac{1}{\mathcal{M}}(-\mathbf{h}\mathbf{q} - k_x x + f_e + f_u), & (1a) \\ \dot{x} = v, & (1b) \\ \dot{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{g}v, & (1c) \\ y = v, & (1d) \end{cases}$$

where x is displacement, v is velocity, $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_r}$ are the radiation states, with the associated radiation triple $(\mathbf{F}, \mathbf{g}, \mathbf{h})$ being passive [15], and f_e is the wave excitation force. Let $\mathbf{x}^\top = [z, v, \mathbf{z}_r^\top]$, and rewrite system (1), concisely, as:

$$\Sigma_w : \begin{cases} \dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{B}(f_e + f_u), & (2a) \\ y = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}. & (2b) \end{cases}$$

B. Impedance matching principle

In wave energy systems, the absorbed mechanical energy is employed as the control objective for the development of *mechanical energy maximising* control

strategies. For system (1), the integral of converted power over the interval $T \in \mathbb{R}_+$ is given by:

$$\mathcal{J}_T = - \int_T f_u v(\tau) d\tau. \quad (3)$$

To solve for the control action f_u that maximises (3), the impedance matching principle is typically used [16]. This solution is obtained in the frequency domain, using the velocity to force response from (2) in the Fourier domain as:

$$Z(j\omega) = \frac{F_e - F_u}{V}(j\omega), \quad (4)$$

where $Z(j\omega)$ is termed the WEC intrinsic impedance, and F_e , F_u , and V , are the Fourier transform pairs of the wave excitation force, control action, and velocity, respectively. Then, the control force that maximises (3) may be designed as:

$$F_u(j\omega) = -V(j\omega) Z^*(j\omega), \quad (5)$$

where $Z^*(j\omega)$ is the complex conjugate of the WEC intrinsic impedance. It is well known that the solution in (5) is not realisable for panchromatic wave excitation, since the analytic continuation of (5) is either uncausal or unstable [17]. However, note that, by replacing (5) in (4), it is possible to obtain the force-to-velocity closed-loop transfer function:

$$T(j\omega) = \frac{V}{F_{ex}}(j\omega) = \frac{1}{Z(j\omega) + Z^*(j\omega)} = \frac{1}{2 \operatorname{Re}\{Z(j\omega)\}}, \quad (6)$$

from which the following conditions, employed for the design of controllers for WECs, may be stated:

- (C1) **Phase condition:** The optimal WEC velocity is (frequency-wise) proportional to the wave excitation force.
- (C2) **Amplitude condition:** The proportionality factor between the optimal velocity and the wave excitation force is, in the frequency domain, the transform pair of $1/2 \operatorname{Re}\{Z(j\omega)\}$.

To approximate, in real-time, the optimal control force from (5), various controllers [7] [10] [11] [12] [18] have been proposed. Also, suboptimal strategies that achieve (C1) solely, designed to synchronise the WEC velocity with the wave excitation force, can be found in [19] [20].

As detailed in the following section, Symphony is designed to approximately satisfy (C1). The rationale behind considering (C1) only can be explained as follows. Simultaneously satisfying conditions (C1) and (C2) results in significant motion amplification of the WECs, leading to amplitudes, velocities, and control forces that can easily exceed the WEC physical limits [21] [22], which is especially concerning in the absence of hard constraint management. Consequently, for any energy-maximizing controller for WECs, handling constraints becomes essential, and, while the amplitude condition (C2) may not be satisfied, the phase condition (C1) remains crucial.

III. SYMPHONY: SIMPLE PHASE CONTROL

The Symphony controller scheme is presented in Figure 1. Essentially, Symphony is composed of four main subsystems. A velocity reference generation block, a tracking controller, and two auxiliary reference conditioning methods, designed to handle hard position, velocity, and force constraints. In the following, the reference generation block is presented and discussed in Subsection III-A, the tracking controller is presented in Subsection III-B, and finally, the constraint methods are presented in Subsections III-C and III-D.

Figure 1. Symphony controller block diagram. Note the combined operation of the feedforward and feedback controllers.

A. Generation of the velocity reference

For the design of the velocity reference, assume, without loss of generality, that $f_{ex}(t)$ is known (provided $f_{ex}(t)$ may be obtained using an estimator [23] [24] [25] [26]). Then, the Symphony velocity reference, $v^*(t)$, is designed to satisfy (C1) using:

$$v^*(t) = f_{ex}(t) \cdot k_0(t), \quad (7)$$

with $k_0(t) : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ being a design parameter. By defining $v^*(t)$ as in (7), the main control objective is to synchronise the WEC velocity with the excitation force.

Observe that the proportionality factor, $k_0(t)$, plays a fundamental role. To design $k_0(t)$, two options are proposed:

- A constant k_0 , found by resorting to empirical evaluation, may be employed. Using this option defines a Symphony structure with performance **independent** of the WEC model, since, with a constant k_0 , $v^*(t)$ is independent of the WEC model.
- If an approximate model for the radiation system is available, it is possible to set a slowly-varying $k_0(t)$, which is aimed at maximising, over a time-moving window, the absorbed energy.

To obtain a slowly varying $k_0(t)$, modify cost function (3), by including a terminal cost value as follows:

$$\mathcal{J}(t) = \mathcal{E}_t - \mathcal{E}_{t_0} - \int_{t_0}^t f_u \dot{z}(\tau) d\tau, \quad (8)$$

where \mathcal{E}_t is the energy stored in the WEC at time t (i.e., kinetic and potential energy). Then, substituting

(1a) and (7) into (8), leads to expressing (8) only as a function of v^* :

$$\mathcal{E}_t - \mathcal{E}_{t_0} - \int_{t_0}^t f_u \dot{z}(\tau) d\tau = \int_{t_0}^t v^* f_{ex}(\tau) - v^* f_r(v^*)(\tau) d\tau.$$

Then, with a slowly varying $k_0(t)$, cost function (8) may be computed as a function of $k_0(t)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}_t - \mathcal{E}_{t_0} - \int_{t_0}^t f_u \dot{z}(\tau) d\tau &\approx \\ &\approx \int_{t_0}^t k_0(\tau) \underbrace{f_{ex}^2(\tau)}_{T_2(\tau)} - k_0^2(\tau) \underbrace{f_{ex} \cdot f_r(f_{ex})(\tau)}_{T_1(\tau)} d\tau, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

with $f_r(f_{ex})$ being the radiation force evaluated using $f_{ex}(t)$ as input (rather than $v(t)$). Note that, in (9), the terms $T_1(t)$ and $T_2(t)$ are independent of $k_0(t)$. Then, it is proposed to maximise the right-hand-side of (9) over an exponentially weighted moving window:

$$\int_{t_0}^t (k_0(\tau) T_2(\tau) - k_0^2(\tau) T_1(\tau)) e^{-q(t-\tau)} d\tau, \quad (10)$$

where $q > 0$ is a forgetting factor, included to focus on current energy, with decreasing emphasis on past values. Then, differentiating (10) with respect to $k_0(t)$, the $k_0(t)$ that maximises (10) is obtained:

$$k_0(t) = \frac{\int_{t_0}^t f_{ex}^2 e^{-q(t-\tau)} d\tau}{2 \int_{t_0}^t f_{ex} f_r(f_{ex}) e^{-q(t-\tau)} d\tau}. \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) calculates slow variations for $k_0(t)$ which follow the variations of the wave climate (due to the $f_{ex}(t)$ dependence). Observe that, in (11), the only dependence on the WEC parameters is on the radiation force, $f_r(\cdot)$. Thus, approximation (11) is *insensitive* to modelling errors in the WEC mass and restoring coefficients.

B. Tracking control design

In this paper, due to appealing tracking capabilities and inherent robustness, SM control [27] is employed. The proposed tracking controller is a natural extension of that presented in [28], but is easy to tune, possesses improved noise rejection capabilities, and has smoother control action, since the discontinuous SM control action appears only on the second time derivative of the control signal. For further discussions on this topic, the reader is referred to [26] [29] [30]. Specifically, the proposed SM control law is:

$$\dot{w}_1 = w_2 - k_1[w_1]^{4/5}, \quad (12a)$$

$$\dot{w}_2 = v - v^* - k_2[w_1]^{3/5}, \quad (12b)$$

$$\Delta f_u = \nu_1 = \nu_2 - k_3[w_1]^{2/5}, \quad (12c)$$

$$\dot{\nu}_2 = \nu_3 - k_4[w_1]^{1/5}, \quad (12d)$$

$$\dot{\nu}_3 = -k_5[w_1]^0, \quad (12e)$$

where ν_1 is the control action, the parameters k_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$ are to-be-designed gains, and the notation $[\cdot]^j = |\cdot|^j \text{sign}(\cdot)$ is employed.

To tune the controller, given an $L \in \mathbb{R}_+$, an appropriate selection of the gains k_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, is [29]:

$$k_1 = 5 \cdot L^{1/5}, \quad (13a)$$

$$k_2 = 10.03 \cdot L^{2/5}, \quad (13b)$$

$$k_3 = 9.3 \cdot L^{3/5}/M, \quad (13c)$$

$$k_4 = 4.57 \cdot L^{4/5}/M, \quad (13d)$$

$$k_5 = 1.1 \cdot L/M, \quad (13e)$$

with L being a design parameter. To find L , it is advisable to resort to in-silico evaluation, analysing different initial condition errors and unmodelled dynamics. Then, employing (13), after some finite time, T , $v = v^*$ is achieved, and the control robustly follows the reference $\forall t > T$ [31] [32].

C. Reference conditioning method for position constraints

In order to design a position constraint method that preserves the proportionality between v^* and f_e , a multiplicative reference conditioning method is proposed. Specifically, let the conditioned velocity reference, \tilde{v}^* , be:

$$\tilde{v}^* = f_{ex}(t) \cdot k_0(t) \underbrace{\frac{e^{-\left(\frac{z}{z_M}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{v}{v_M}\right)^2 - \frac{zv}{c}} - e^{-1}}{1 - e^{-1}}}_{f(z,v)}, \quad (14)$$

with $c, z_M, v_M \in \mathbb{R}_+$ being user-defined variables. In (14), $f(z, v)$ is an envelope modulation function, included to handle position and velocity constraints. The rationale behind including $f(z, v)$ in (14) is justified as follows. Considering that the WEC is controlled via the scheme from Figure 1, the dynamics of the WEC position, with $\dot{z} \equiv v$, are:

$$\dot{z} = f_{ex}(t) \cdot k_0(t) f(z, \dot{z}), \quad (15)$$

which is guaranteed by employing a robust tracking controller¹. Let z_M be a hard constraint:

$$|z(t)| \leq z_M. \quad (16)$$

With the position dynamics of (15), position constraint (16) is satisfied $\forall t$, if, as $z \rightarrow z_M$, the controlled system velocity approaches zero, holding the WEC still. Observe that this is achieved with (14), since $k(t) \rightarrow 0$, as $z \rightarrow z_M$. Additionally, in (15), $k(t) \rightarrow 0$ for $v \rightarrow v_M$. That is, the envelope function $f(z, v)$ satisfies position constraint (16), but also prevents the WEC velocity from surpassing a maximum velocity, function of v_M [33]. An illustrative $f(z, v)$, based on (14), is shown in Figure 2.

D. Reference conditioning method for force constraints

Using the control scheme in Figure 1, the position constraints are satisfied by means of $f(z, v)$. However,

¹Studying the level and nature of robustness of the tracking controller required to satisfactorily guarantee (15) is beyond the scope of the present paper. In particular, in this paper, sliding mode algorithms are recommended due to their inherent robustness to satisfy (15).

Figure 2. Illustrative $f(z, v)$ using $c = 15$, $z_M = 3m$, and $v_M = 4m/s$.

tracking \tilde{v}^* may require large PTO control forces, while typically, the control action f_u must satisfy:

$$|f_u(t)| \leq f_M. \quad (17)$$

In this section, a hard constraint mechanism, based on SM, that satisfies (17) $\forall t$, is presented.

SM reference conditioning (SMRC) is a force constraint method that, to satisfy constraint (17), penalises v^* . However, SMRC only acts within a user-defined manifold, when f_u approaches the constraint limits. In essence, the SMRC loop is composed of three subsystems (see Figure 1). (i) A user-defined switching function $\sigma(\cdot)$, (ii) a commutation block where a discontinuous action is implemented, and (iii) a low-pass filter (LPF), which provides a smooth SMRC output, w_s . Additionally, assume that the control force may be saturated, and define the saturated control force \bar{f}_u as:

$$\bar{f}_u = \begin{cases} f_M & \text{if } f_u > f_M, \\ f_u & \text{if } -f_M < f_u < f_M, \\ -f_M & \text{if } f_u < -f_M, \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

with $f_M \in \mathbb{R}_+$. The main objective of SMRC is to limit the control force, f_u , between two surfaces, \bar{S} and \underline{S} , defined by the switching function $\sigma(\cdot)$, and designed to ensure constraint (17). Formally, \bar{S} and \underline{S} are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{S} &= \{x_c \in \mathcal{X}_c : \sigma|_{\bar{f}_u=f_M} = 0\}, \\ \underline{S} &= \{x_c \in \mathcal{X}_c : \sigma|_{\bar{f}_u=-f_M} = 0\}, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where $x_c \in \mathcal{X}_c \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is the tracking controller state. In words, by keeping the control variables between the surfaces defined by \bar{S} and \underline{S} , the controller operational space is limited to satisfy constraint (17). To force $\sigma = 0$, when the control force, f_u , approaches the constraint limits, the discontinuous signal, w ,

$$w = \begin{cases} w^+ & \text{if } \sigma < 0 \\ w^- & \text{if } \sigma > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } \sigma = 0 \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

is implemented in the commutation block. An illustrative SMRC operational scheme is presented in Figure 3. Note that, if x_c is between \bar{S} , \underline{S} , then $\sigma = 0$, $w = 0$, and the reference is not modified (SMRC is not active). However, when x_c reaches \bar{S} , or \underline{S} , w becomes nonzero, driving the control force to $\sigma = 0$, and preventing

Figure 3. Graphical interpretation of the SMRC operation.

$f_u = C_c x_c$ from exceeding the specified constraints. For effective operation of SMRC, the following conditions are required:

- (C3) **Transversality condition** [34]. The switching function σ is of unitary relative degree with respect to the discontinuous action (σ must be an explicit function of w),
- (C4) **Gain condition** [34]. The amplitudes w^+ , w^- , satisfy:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 < \underline{w}_{eq} < w^+, \\ w^- < \bar{w}_{eq} < 0, \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where \underline{w}_{eq} and \bar{w}_{eq} are the theoretically continuous actions that would keep the control force between \underline{S} and \bar{S} .

While w^+ , w^- , may be empirically selected to satisfy (C4), the relative degree condition, (C3), typically requires an analysis of the variables in the considered application [35].

IV. SYMPHONY CONTROLLER NUMERICAL EVALUATION

In this section, in-silico studies are conducted to evaluate Symphony control performance. To that end, the simulation parameters are detailed in Subsection IV-A. Then, time domain results are presented in Subsection IV-B. Finally, in Subsection IV-C, the Symphony performance is assessed in terms of energy absorption and computation time.

A. Simulation parameters

In this section, the parameters and assumptions required to evaluate Symphony performance are presented and briefly discussed.

1) **WEC model:** The Symphony controller is evaluated on a Corepower-like WEC device [36], illustrated in Figure 4. By assuming linear hydrodynamics, and one-degree-of-freedom motion, the WEC dynamics are given by (1), where \mathcal{M} and k_x are presented in Table I, and \mathbf{F} , \mathbf{g} , and \mathbf{h} are:

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} -7 & -24 & -47 & -57 & -43 & -18 & -3.4 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (22a)$$

$$\mathbf{g} = [1.46 \cdot 10^5 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]^T, \quad (22b)$$

$$\mathbf{h} = [0.21 \ 1.1 \ 3.8 \ 4.6 \ 3 \ 0.64 \ 0.014] \cdot 10^{-5}. \quad (22c)$$

Figure 4. Schematic illustration of the point absorber WEC device. SWL denotes the 'still water level'.

 Table I
 NOMINAL SYSTEM MODEL AND SM CONTROL PARAMETERS

WEC parameters		
$\mathcal{M} = 6.8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ kg}^{-1}$	$k_x = 5.57 \times 10^5 \text{ N/m}$	$n_r = 7$
Parameter	SM controller	
L	6 m/s ³	
k_5	1.1 L/M	
k_4	4.57 L ^{4/5} /M	
k_3	9.3 L ^{3/5} /M	
k_2	10.03 L ^{2/5}	
k_1	5 L ^{1/5}	
Parameter	SMRC force constraint	
$w^+ = -w^-$	1.5 m/Ns	
LPF cutoff frequency λ_F	10	

2) **Sea state realisations:** To generate a realistic wave profile, a Bretschneider spectrum, considering peak wave periods $T_p \in [5, 5.2, 5.4, \dots, 9]$ s, and significant wave height $H_s = 1.2$ m, is employed [37]. To obtain statistically representative results, for each sea state, 30 realisations of 1200s are generated.

3) **Symphony controller tuning:** For the WEC under study, assume that the position and force constraints are:

$$|z(t)| \leq 2\text{m} = z_M, \quad (23)$$

$$|f_u(t)| \leq 0.8 \cdot 10^6 \text{ N} = f_M. \quad (24)$$

Thus, first, to robustly satisfy position constraint (23), two Symphony configurations are used:

- Symphony_{I} (independent), tuned with $c = 15$, $v_M = 12\text{m/s}$ for Section IV-C1, $v_M = 2.1\text{m/s}$ for Section IV-C2, and using a constant $k_0 = 4.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$. This configuration defines a Symphony control structure completely independent of the WEC model.
- Symphony_{S} (standard), tuned with $c = 15$, $v_M = 12\text{m/s}$ for Section IV-C1, $v_M = 2.1\text{m/s}$ for Section IV-C2, and using (14) for $k_0(t)$. This configuration only requires an approximate radiation model.

Second, to robustly satisfy force constraint (24), for both Symphony_{S,I} configurations, the SMRC force constraint method, tuned with the parameters presented in Table I, is used. Table I also presents the tracking controller parameters. To evaluate the comparative

computational burden, all simulations are conducted using a notebook with an Intel CORE i5 processor.

4) *Benchmark controllers for comparison*: In order to critically assess the results obtained with Symphony, two OB controllers are employed:

- An MPC controller, following the design presented in [2] [38], with a sampling period of 0.125s, and a prediction and control horizon of 60 samples.
- A PS controller designed as in [3] [6] [39].

It is important to note that the performance of both PS and MPC algorithms is highly dependent on the model precision and tuning parameters [6] [40]. Only in the best-case scenario, MPC and PS provide a target reference for the maximum achievable power absorption. Additionally, note that, to implement PS control in real time, a receding-horizon strategy is typically required [6] [41]. For a deeper understanding of the differences between MPC and PS, the reader is kindly referred to [6]. In the results presented in this section, perfect knowledge of f_e , and the required forecast, is assumed.

B. Time domain analysis

A time trace of the position, velocity and control force, obtained with controllers PS, MPC, and Symphony_I, is presented in Figure 5. The plotted variables correspond to a sea state with $T_p = 8s$. First, it is noted that every control satisfies the constraints requirements for both position (in Figure 5 (top)), and force (in Figure 5 (bottom)). In addition, it can be seen that the time evolution of the MPC and PS variables is similar, with subtle differences inherently produced by the differences in the discretisation procedures [6]. Note that, the time evolution of Symphony_I variables, position, velocity, and control action, is smoother, presenting fewer variations than in the PS and MPC cases.

In Figure 6, the absorbed energy, using $T_p = 8s$, is presented. Here, it is possible to appreciate the effectiveness of Symphony_I: Above 90% of the OB reference is obtained, although Symphony is a non-OB control, with causal constraint mechanisms. Additionally, observe that, while Symphony operates using an f_e estimate, both PS and MPC require an f_e forecast. Hence, in practice, due to forecasting errors, a degradation of PS and MPC performance is also expected.

C. Average power absorption in constrained scenarios

In this section, with position and force constraints given by (23) and (24), the Symphony performance is evaluated. First, in Subsection IV-C1, it is assumed that only position constraints are required. Second, both position and force constraints are used in Subsection IV-C2.

1) Power absorption with position constraint:

In this section, the average power absorption of Symphony_{S,I} is compared with the OB controllers MPC and PS.

First, note, in Figure 7, that the OB reference solutions are different alternatives to solve the same

Figure 5. Average power extraction in the unconstrained case. Comparison between MPC, SP, and Symphony_{S}.

Figure 6. Time evolution of the absorbed energy. The results illustrate, overlapped, the absorbed energy for the MPC, PS, and Symphony_{S} controllers, for $T_p = 8s$.

optimisation problem. Hence, the performance in terms of power absorption of both PS and MPC controllers is, on average, the same. On the other hand, Symphony_S provides close-to-optimal performance (above 90%) with the following advantages:

- OB controllers require exact knowledge of the system, but Symphony_S only requires an approximate radiation model. Hence, it is expected that, considering model uncertainty, the performance of OB controllers will be degraded, while Symphony_S is likely to preserve nominal performance. This aspect will be addressed on future research.

Figure 7. Average power absorption with position constraints. Comparison between OB strategies PS and MPC (overlapped) and the $\text{Symphony}_{\{S,I\}}$ configurations.

- OB controllers require an f_e forecast, while symphony only requires an instantaneous f_e estimate.
- Symphony is, in terms of computational burden, the controller with the best results (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. Average computation time for 30 realisations of 100s with $T_p = 6s$. Comparison between MPC, PS and Symphony.

Some additional remarks are in order. First, note that Symphony depends on the length of the exponential window (with its associated forgetting factor, q), the velocity limit, v_M , and the selected $k_0(t)$. However, in this paper, q , v_M , and k_0 , have been empirically selected without resorting to complex optimisation routines. Hence, potentially, Symphony could be further improved. For the time being, however, studying the effects of varying q , and v_M , on average power absorption, is beyond the scope of this paper.

It is particularly interesting to assess Symphony_I performance, which is still close-to-optimal (above 90% for most sea states), highlighting that the envelope function $f(z, v)$ governs the WEC response in con-

Figure 9. Average power absorption with position and force constraints. Comparison between OB strategies and the $\text{Symphony}_{\{S,I\}}$ configurations.

strained scenarios: Using $k_0(t)$, tuned with (11), results in large gains that are then diminished by $f(z, v)$ to satisfy the position and constraint requirements. Hence, significantly, Symphony can be designed as a controller whose robustness and performance are independent of the WEC parameters.

2) *Power absorption with position and force constraints:* In this section, the force constraint, f_M , is given by (24), and the OB controllers, PS and MPC, average power absorption is presented and compared with the $\text{Symphony}_{\{S,I\}}$ from Subsection IV-C1. Note that, in this section, $\text{Symphony}_{\{S,I\}}$ is tuned with v_M set to $2.1m/s$ (unlike in the previous Section IV-C1, where $v_M = 12m/s$). This is because when force constraints are considered, the maximum velocity is reduced to achieve higher levels of power absorption.

In this scenario, the Symphony performance is within 95-85% of the OB references (see Figure 9). Hence, it is appreciated that there is a degradation in the Symphony performance with respect to the case with only position constraints. This may be attributed to the SMRC force constraint mechanism, which does not *anticipate* saturation in the control action. Instead, SMRC is only active when the control force reaches the constraint. Nevertheless, Symphony still outperforms OB controllers in terms of computational burden (As presented in Figure 8), and simplicity, while retaining close-to-optimal performance without requiring precise model information. Additionally, recall that the computational burden of MPC and PS is not constant. With larger peak wave periods, MPS and PS optimal solutions are closer to the constraint limits, and this results in increased computational burden. In contrast, the computational burden of Symphony is constant for

the considered peak wave periods and approximately two orders of magnitude smaller than the evaluated OB solutions.

Another pertinent remark is as follows. To satisfy hard position constraints, PS control may become computationally intractable for real-time operation. A similar observation can be made with respect to MPC control; while MPC is a closed-loop strategy, only force constraints may be robustly satisfied, since model mismatch and uncertainty, combined with the time discretisation in MPC, may result in unsatisfactory position constraints handling [6]. Conversely, Symphony, in addition to its close-to-optimal performance, is capable of robustly satisfying hard position and force constraints without the necessity of adjusting any control parameter.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, Symphony, a novel non-OB controller for wave energy systems is presented. The amalgamation of simple control concepts provide Symphony with close-to-optimal performance, combined with robustness and simplicity of implementation, design, and tuning. Specifically, by employing a robust controller, Symphony is designed to track a velocity proportional to the excitation force. Then, to handle position and velocity constraints, Symphony incorporates a Gaussian modulation function that retains synchronisation between the excitation force and the WEC velocity. Additionally, to robustly satisfy force constraints, an SMRC force constraint mechanism is included.

The obtained results exemplify the efficacy of the proposal. In terms of power absorption, Symphony is the first non-OB controller that obtains close-to-optimal performance ($> 90\%$) in constrained scenarios, and across varying sea states, with minimum recalibration. In terms of time domain performance, Symphony is the first non-OB controller capable of causally and robustly handling hard position, velocity, and force constraints. Moreover, unlike OB controllers, Symphony is largely independent of the WEC model, which represents a seminal advancement, especially considering the difficulties in accurate control-oriented hydrodynamic modelling for WECs [40]. In summary, Symphony represents a new benchmark for controller performance evaluation and a promising alternative for real-time WEC control and co-design evaluation, not only for its simplicity and robustness, but also for its close-to-optimal constrained performance, with inherent independence with respect to model uncertainties.

Lastly, critical areas for future development include extending the Symphony controller principles of operation for WEC array control, evaluating its use for multiple degree-of-freedom WECs, assessing the effects of including wave excitation force estimation in the control loop, and using Symphony as a benchmark controller for control co-design evaluation.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Faedo, S. Olaya, and J. V. Ringwood, "Optimal control, MPC and MPC-like algorithms for wave energy systems: An overview," *IFAC Journal of Systems and Control*, vol. 1, pp. 37-56, Sep. 2017.
- [2] Z. Lin, X. Huang, and X. Xiao, "Fast model predictive control system for wave energy converters with wave tank tests," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 70, no. 7, pp. 6887-6897, 2022.
- [3] D. Garcia-Violini and J. V. Ringwood, "Energy maximising robust control for spectral and pseudospectral methods with application to wave energy systems," *International Journal of Control*, vol. 94, no. 4, pp. 1102-1113, Jun. 2019.
- [4] N. Faedo, Y. Pena-Sanchez, and J. V. Ringwood, "Receding-horizon energy-maximising optimal control of wave energy systems based on moments," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 378-386, Jan. 2021.
- [5] Z. Lin, X. Huang, X. Xiao, and J. V. Ringwood, "A sensitivity analysis of wave energy converter model predictive control systems with wave excitation force estimation and prediction," *IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 136-147, 2024.
- [6] R. Genest and J. V. Ringwood, "A critical comparison of model-predictive and pseudospectral control for wave energy devices," *Journal of Ocean Engineering and Marine Energy*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 485-499, 2016.
- [7] D. García-Violini, N. Faedo, F. Jaramillo-Lopez, and J. V. Ringwood, "Simple controllers for wave energy devices compared," *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 10, p. 793, Oct. 2020.
- [8] X. Huang, Z. Lin, and X. Xiao, "Simple and low-model-dependent strategy for the economic and safe control of direct-drive wave energy converters," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 2263-2272, 2023.
- [9] D. Garcia-Violini, Y. Pena-Sanchez, N. Faedo, and J. V. Ringwood, "An energy-maximising linear time invariant controller (LiTe-Con) for wave energy devices," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 2713-2721, Oct. 2020.
- [10] D. García-Violini, Y. Peña-Sanchez, N. Faedo, F. Ferri, and J. V. Ringwood, "A broadband time-varying energy maximising control for wave energy systems (LiTe-Con+): Framework and experimental assessment," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 1516-1525, Jul. 2023.
- [11] G. Bacelli, V. Nevarez, R. G. Coe, and D. G. Wilson, "Feedback resonating control for a wave energy converter," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 1862-1868, Mar. 2020.
- [12] F. Fusco and J. V. Ringwood, "A simple and effective real-time controller for wave energy converters," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 21-30, Jan. 2013.
- [13] J. V. Ringwood, A. Merigaud, N. Faedo, and F. Fusco, "An analytical and numerical sensitivity and robustness analysis of wave energy control systems," *IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 1337-1348, Jul. 2020.
- [14] J. Falnes and A. Kurniawan, *Ocean Waves And Oscillating Systems: Linear Interactions Including Wave-Energy Extraction*. Cambridge University Press, 2020, vol. 8.
- [15] T. Pérez and T. I. Fossen, "Time-vs. frequency-domain identification of parametric radiation force models for marine structures at zero speed," *Model. Identif. Control*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 1-19, 2008.
- [16] J. Falnes, *Ocean Waves and Oscillating Systems: Linear Interaction*. Cambridge University Press, 2002.
- [17] J. Scruggs, "On the causal power generation limit for a vibratory energy harvester in broadband stochastic response," *Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures*, vol. 21, no. 13, pp. 1249-1262, Feb. 2010.
- [18] J. V. Ringwood, G. Bacelli, and F. Fusco, "Energy-maximizing control of wave-energy converters: The development of control system technology to optimize their operation," *IEEE Control Systems*, vol. 34, no. 5, pp. 30-55, Oct. 2014.
- [19] A. Babarit, M. Guglielmi, and A. H. Clément, "Declutching control of a wave energy converter," *Ocean Engineering*, vol. 36, no. 12-13, pp. 1015-1024, Sep. 2009.
- [20] J. Henriques, L. Gato, A. Falcão, E. Robles, and F.-X. Faÿ, "Latching control of a floating oscillating-water-column wave energy converter," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 90, pp. 229-241, May 2016.
- [21] J. V. Ringwood, S. Zhan, and N. Faedo, "Empowering wave energy with control technology: Possibilities and pitfalls," *Annual Reviews in Control*, vol. 55, pp. 18-44, Apr. 2023.
- [22] G. Bacelli and J. V. Ringwood, "A geometric tool for the analysis of position and force constraints in wave energy converters," *Ocean Engineering*, vol. 65, pp. 10-18, Jun. 2013.
- [23] Y. Pena-Sanchez, C. Windt, J. Davidson, and J. V. Ringwood, "A critical comparison of excitation force estimators for wave-

- energy devices," *IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 2263–2275, Nov. 2020.
- [24] N. Faedo, U. Bussi, Y. Peña-Sanchez, C. Windt, and J. V. Ringwood, "A simple and effective excitation force estimator for wave energy systems," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 241–250, Jan. 2022.
- [25] F. D. Mosquera, P. Fornaro, P. F. Puleston, C. A. Evangelista, and J. V. Ringwood, "A sliding mode-based tracking observer for excitation force estimation in wave energy systems," in *Conference on Control Technology and Applications (CCTA)*, Newcastle, UK, Aug. 2024.
- [26] P. Fornaro, F. D. Mosquera, P. F. Puleston, C. A. Evangelista, and J. V. Ringwood, "Homogeneous filtering unknown input observer for wave energy applications," in *63rd IEEE Conference on Decision and Control*, Milan, Italy, Dec. 2024.
- [27] Y. Shtessel, C. Edwards, L. Fridman, and A. Levant, *Sliding Mode Control and Observation*. Springer New York, 2013.
- [28] N. Faedo, F. D. Mosquera, E. Pasta, G. Papini, Y. Peña-Sanchez, C. A. Evangelista, F. Ferri, J. V. Ringwood, and P. Puleston, "Experimental assessment of combined sliding mode & moment-based control (SM²C) for arrays of wave energy conversion systems," *Control Engineering Practice*, vol. 144, p. 105818, Mar. 2024.
- [29] A. Levant and M. Livne, "Robust exact filtering differentiators," *Eur. J. Control*, vol. 55, pp. 33–44, Sep. 2019.
- [30] P. Fornaro, F. D. Mosquera, C. A. Evangelista, P. F. Puleston, and J. V. Ringwood, "A filtering super-twisting controller with noise rejection," in *64th IEEE Conference on Decision and Control*, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, Dec. 2025.
- [31] Y. V. Orlov, Ed., *Discontinuous Systems*, ser. SpringerLink. London: Springer London, 2009.
- [32] A. Levant and M. Livne, "Weighted homogeneity and robustness of sliding mode control," *Automatica*, vol. 72, pp. 186–193, Oct. 2016.
- [33] J. L. Anderson, P. Fornaro, P. F. Puleston, and J. V. Ringwood, "A causal approach to hard constrained control of wave energy systems based on implicit gaussian differential equation," in *64th IEEE Conference on Decision and Control*, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, Dec. 2025.
- [34] C. Edwards and S. Spurgeon, *Sliding Mode Control: Theory and Applications*. London: Crc Press, 1998.
- [35] P. Fornaro, P. Muñoz, S. A. González, P. F. Puleston, and J. V. Ringwood, "Sliding mode reference conditioning force constraint mechanism for closed-loop wave energy controllers," in *29th Argentinian conference on Automatic Control*, Córdoba, Argentina, Aug. 2025.
- [36] J. H. Todalshaug, G. S. Ásgeirsson, E. Hjalmarsson, J. Maillet, P. Möller, P. Pires, M. Guérinel, and M. Lopes, "Tank testing of an inherently phase-controlled wave energy converter," *International Journal of Marine Energy*, vol. 15, pp. 68–84, Sep. 2016.
- [37] C. L. Bretschneider, *Wave variability and wave spectra for wind-generated gravity waves*. USA: The Board, 1959, no. 118.
- [38] Z. Lin, X. Huang, X. Xiao, and J. V. Ringwood, "Fast optimal control performance evaluation for wave energy control co-design," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 239, p. 121974, 2025.
- [39] G. Bacelli and J. V. Ringwood, "Numerical optimal control of wave energy converters," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 294–302, Apr. 2015.
- [40] C. Windt, N. Faedo, M. Penalba, F. Dias, and J. V. Ringwood, "Reactive control of wave energy devices – the modelling paradox," *Applied Ocean Research*, vol. 109, p. 102574, Apr. 2021.
- [41] A. Mérigaud and J. V. Ringwood, "Towards realistic non-linear receding-horizon spectral control of wave energy converters," *Control Engineering Practice*, vol. 81, pp. 145–161, 2018.